
**Deliverable D-WP6.2 – A
practical manual to the use
of dashboards in One Health
Surveillance practice,
including recommendations
for sustainability**

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Contributing partners: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR,
13-SSI, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 28-IZSAM, 33-
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D-WP6.2

A practical manual to the use of dashboards in OHS practice, including recommendations for sustainability

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Abbreviations

AH:	Animal Health
AMR:	Antimicrobial Resistance
CSS:	Cascading Style Sheets
DIC:	Dashboard Information Centre
DSL:	Domain-Specific Language
FCL:	Food Chain-Lab
FS:	Food Safety
GENPAT:	National Reference Centre for Whole Genome Sequencing of Microbial Pathogens: Database and Bioinformatic Analysis
HTML:	Hypertext Markup Language
IT:	Information Technology
JS:	JavaScript
JSON:	JavaScript Object Notation
KNIME:	Konstanz Information Miner
LIMS:	Laboratory Information Management System
MCMC:	Markov Chain Monte Carlo
OH:	One Health
OHEJP:	One Health European Joint Programme
OHS:	One Health Surveillance
PH:	Public Health
SQL:	Structured Query Language
TSIS:	TierSeuchenInformations-System / Animal Diseases Information System
TSN:	TierSeuchenNachrichten-System / Animal Disease News System
WAHIS:	World Animal Health Information System
WGS:	Whole-Genome Sequencing
WP:	Work Package

Introduction

One Health Surveillance (OHS) is the combination of health surveillance data and knowledge from the three health sectors — public health (PH), animal health (AH) and food safety (FS) — in order to understand how the health of humans, animals and the environment are connected and affect each other.

MATRIX is a project of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), a partnership of 44 food, veterinary and medical laboratories and institutes across Europe and the Med-Vet-Net Association. MATRIX connects existing cross-sectorial One Health programmes in European countries. Today, 19 partner institutes representing the AH, PH and FS sectors from 12 countries continue a collaboration that started early in 2020 and will end in December 2022. More information can be found here.

The purpose of MATRIX is to create practical solutions for European countries to support and to advance the implementation of OHS. MATRIX invites European institutes working in the AH, PH and FS sectors to consider the opportunity to adopt these solutions and to further build upon them.

Work Package (WP) 6 focuses on visualisation of OHS inputs and outputs for the use of surveillance officials in PH, AH and FS. This is achieved through the creation of dashboards, which include surveillance data from all three sectors.

A dashboard is a form of graphical user interface which displays data and metrics in a way that facilitates tracking, analysis and monitoring to inform decision-making. A disease surveillance dashboard might contain charts, tables, maps or other elements providing a comprehensive overview of the development of the disease in question, or even predicting future outbreak events.

The [ORION](#) project has identified data sources that are already public or shared across sectors. The [NOVA](#) project has built automated routines for data analyses and visualisation when trend monitoring is possible. The MATRIX project builds on these results and the experience gained through the dashboard development work to create an information centre which will serve as a best-practice guide for OHS dashboards; the Dashboard Information Centre ([DIC](#)). This will document important aspects such as:

- Information context and end-user considerations: what information does a user or a surveillance official need on their everyday work, and in case of emergency? What kind of data can provide that information?
- Step by step guide for developing dashboards
- Possible pitfalls and biases when One Health data is co-analysed
- Example of an open-source technical solution based on the data, available resources and desired outcomes
- Contact information for experts within MATRIX with knowledge in relevant topics

This information centre will also function as an inventory and showcase of all planned, ongoing and finished dashboard activities within MATRIX, so that the provided information can be exemplified by real-world implementations.

In this deliverable we present various dashboards and interactive tools that are in place or are being developed by member institutes of MATRIX WP6.

The participants in the WP were in varying stages of dashboard development. Some of the participants had no dashboard projects planned, as they do not have enough finances or personnel for the near future, but they wanted to be a part of this WP to be able to learn and prepare for the future planning of an institutional or national dashboard project. Other participants did have dashboards within their institute but were not able to specifically produce a One Health (OH) dashboard within the time of this project. Still, there were some members who did produce (or start producing) OH dashboards within the project period and were able to reach the pilot stage of development. Despite the large span of experience, knowledge and development in each institute, all the WP participants did know about dashboards and had experience with them – either as users or as developers – and could therefore be a useful resource for this project. In this sense, the group was quite a diverse one whose different view and expertise all added value to the final outcomes of the WP. All the participants have knowledge of OH work and the discussions have been focusing on OHS and dashboards, even though not all countries have operational dashboards as of yet.

Inventory of Dashboards and Tools

BIKE (Ruokavirasto, Finland)

BIKE is a probabilistic dietary exposure assessment model for microbiological hazards (acute exposures) and chemical hazards (chronic exposures) in food, aimed for risk assessment professionals doing quantitative assessments. It is downloadable and open source, providing dashboard features in a graphical user interface (Shiny App). Once downloaded, the user can run the model in their local computer with their own data, to obtain results on estimated exposure (& concentration- & consumption-) distributions and the associated uncertainty implied by the quantity and accuracy of data.

1.1. Data

Consumption data for named food types and hazard occurrence data for the same food types.

1.2. Layout

The user is required to provide data on dietary records for a representative sample of individuals for at least two days per individual, showing the consumed amounts (positive or zero) of each named food type per day. Additionally, hazard concentrations (a set of measurements) and possibly hazard prevalence data for the corresponding food types are needed. A few combinations and alternative interpretations of data are allowed, e.g. concerning values below or between measurement limits. Also processing factors can be applied, affecting prevalence and/or concentration at the time of consumption. The BIKE workflow is illustrated in Figure 1.

1.3. Method

The models are based on Bayesian statistical methods and implemented by Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulations. The mathematical models are described in detail in an open journal (Ranta et al, 2021¹), and the corresponding matching model code is available at [GitHub](#).

1.4. Technical implementation

The model utilizes both [R](#) and [OpenBUGS](#), which need to be installed first. The R code reads data from user given files, and then formats and analyses the data. Based on this, it writes a data-specific OpenBUGS code for implementing the Bayesian model simulations, according to the data structure found, and calls OpenBUGS to perform the MCMC simulations accordingly. After the MCMC simulations are done, the results are processed in R, and they are visualised in a local [Shiny](#) app which provides a user interface for interactively investigating the hazard-food exposure pairs, or total exposure from several foods, or concentrations, or consumptions.

¹ Ranta, J., Mikkilä, A., Suomi, J., Tuominen, P., 2021. BIKE: Dietary Exposure Model for Foodborne Microbiological and Chemical Hazards. *Foods* 10, 2520. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10112520>

Figure 1. Illustration of BIKE probabilistic dietary exposure assessment model for microbiological hazards and chemical hazards in food. BIKE, Ruokavirasto, Finland.

Disease Dashboards (SVA, Sweden)

The National Veterinary Institute (SVA) is the largest veterinary laboratory in Sweden. Every day its microbiology, pathology and sequencing departments analyse a large amount of samples, which in turn produces large amount of data. These data need to be summarised and translated into actionable information in order to fulfil one of the main missions of the institute: surveillance communication. There is a need to effectively communicate the epidemiological situation of Sweden to disease experts, as well as animal owners and the general public.

Surveillance of infectious diseases in animals and humans (“the surveillance report”) is the annual report describing the surveillance activities carried out in Sweden during the year. The report covers surveillance for important animal diseases and zoonotic agents in humans, food, feed and animals, carried out and compiled by experts from several Swedish governmental agencies, university and private industry with surveillance mandates along the entire food chain, from farm to fork. The surveillance report is published by the National Veterinary Institute (SVA), in collaboration with the Swedish Board of Agriculture, the Public Health Agency and the Swedish Food Agency.

To better highlight the important findings presented in the report, and to strengthen the “One Healthness” of the surveillance, SVA is now planning to translate the contents of chapters describing hazards of great interest into interactive online Disease Dashboards. These dashboards will collect all our available knowledge about a specific pathogen, both historically and the current situation.

2.1. Data

The data presented in these disease dashboards will come from two main sources:

- The surveillance report, which provides manually curated datasets and expert analyses on an annual basis. This will provide a historical overview and in-depth conclusions about the status of the disease.
- Internal Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS) and databases, which are updated daily with examination and test results from the laboratories. This will give a snapshot of the current situation, allowing experts to obtain information and take action in a timely and robust manner.

2.2. Layout

The dashboards will be structured as a traditional side-menu website, with different tabs covering different topics. It will have full interactive capabilities, meaning that all data-driven content (maps, tables, graphs, etc.) can be filtered and customised to the user's needs.

2.3. Technical implementation

The dashboard will be developed using a combination of the R language, JavaScript (JS) and Cascading Style Sheets (CSS). An in-house R package has been developed to produce static graphs, maps and tables for the surveillance report; this will be adapted so that it can also be used to create dynamic JavaScript-powered Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) widgets, something which is easily achievable without leaving the R environment. Another in-house R package exists for analysing and summarising the daily lab data, which is currently used to update standalone maps, graphs and tables on the external web; this package will be expanded on to provide content for the disease dashboards. For greater customisation of design and behaviour, a layer of custom JavaScript and CSS will be added on top of the R-generated content. The content will then be brought together into a full web application using the [R Shiny](#) package. The app will be hosted on an internal virtual server and made available through an Internet connection. It will be possible to control the access to the dashboards, ranging from specific users within SVA to the entire public. The plan is to establish a localised access control so that, for example, certain tabs may be available publicly while others require authentication. See Figure 2 for an illustration of the complete dashboard workflow.

Figure 2. Flowchart illustrating the Disease Dashboard workflow (right) and how it builds upon the output of existing workflows (left). Disease Dashboards, SVA, Sweden.

FoodChain-Lab (BfR, Germany)

3.1. Data

FoodChain-Lab (FCL) is a free and open-source software tool aimed to support trace-back and trace-forward analysis of implicated feed or food items along supply chains as well as exposure and risk assessments in foodborne incidents (outbreaks, chemical contaminations). FCL is available here: <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de>.

FCL was created in 2011 and has been running and constantly developing with the support of third projects. From 2023 onward, FCL will be supported by EFSA and BfR for further improvements. FCL Desktop collects and imports data into an internal database by generating semi-filled Excel templates that can be sent to local authorities for data completion and afterwards be imported into the database, or through a direct interface to the database for manual data input. Once the data is transferred into the database it can be validated and updated. FCL Web uses a JSON-based data format and is fed with data from FCL Desktop or other food tracing software systems.

3.2. Layout

A major application of FCL Desktop and FCL Web is the analysis and visualisation of food tracing information. This is accomplished by the construction and visualisation of interactive food chain network graphs consisting of nodes (stations such as food business operators or disease cases) and edges (food product transportation events, deliveries). A score calculated for all stations and deliveries helps to identify the source of a foodborne contamination and prioritize next investigation steps. All visualisations are interactive and can be exported as data tables or images for use in other KNIME nodes, other tools or in reports. See Figure 3 for an FCL visualisation example.

3.3. Technical implementation

The desktop version of FCL has been implemented as a modular extension to the open source data analytics platform Konstanz Information Miner (KNIME). KNIME enables visual assembly of data analysis workflows. These workflows consist of so-called nodes and edges. Each node is able to perform a specific data processing task while edges define how information flow is directed between nodes. FCL is also available as a web application (FCL Web, <https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin/>).

FCL is an open-source software tool that was created in 2011 and has been running and constantly developing with the support of third projects.

As the FCL Desktop version in KNIME and FCL Web are open-source projects, the software code of both tools is available for everybody in the internet and thereby is sustainable in the long-run. The code and the tools are maintained and updated (including new features) since 2011 in the framework of past, current and upcoming research projects and by budget funds of the BfR.

The FCL Web application as ready-to-use tool is hosted in the internet by BfR (<https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin/>) and as one of the flagship projects at BfR, it will also be hosted by BfR in the long-run. And as the software code is available in the long-run, researchers and institutes could also use the code and set up their own sustainable instance of FCL Web.

From 2023 onward, FCL will be more involved in EFSA tasks and in a framework of several European tracing tools; therefore FCL will be supported by EFSA and BfR for further improvements. FCL is sustainable.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Figure 3. FCL Web visualising the supply chain network of a fictitious foodborne disease outbreak in the network view, the map view, the reporting view and in the data table. FoodChain-Lab, BfR, Germany.

GENPAT (IZSAM, Italy)

4.1. Data

The “National Reference Centre for Whole Genome Sequencing of microbial pathogens: database and bioinformatic analysis” ([GENPAT](#)) manages, on behalf of the Italian Ministry of Health, a national platform for collection and sharing of microbial pathogen whole-genome sequencing (WGS) data from animal, food and environmental isolates and for performing bioinformatic analyses.

4.2. Layout

The platform supports and assists the Italian Ministry of Health and competent authorities in technical and scientific claims, providing information technology (IT) tools and data that are quickly available, usable and helpful in outbreak situations allowing to link molecular typing and bioinformatics analyses results with time and position of sampling as well as the other epidemiological information available.

4.3. Technical implementation

The system is a web-based information system with three main components:

- Data component: Based on Cmdbuild, an open-source web enterprise environment used to configure custom applications and to manage databases of items. It has native mechanisms to model its internal database, design workflow, configure reports, build connectors with external systems and so on.
- Calculation engine component: Nextflow enables scalable and reproducible scientific workflows using software containers. It allows the adaptation of pipelines written in the most common scripting languages. Its fluent domain-specific language (DSL) simplifies the implementation and deployment of complex parallel and reactive workflows on clouds and clusters.
- Dashboards component: WGS analysis and metadata are combined in easy-to-use dashboards. For this purpose, a number of well-known, robust open-source projects have been integrated: GrapeTree, PhyloCanvas, OpenStreetMap, OpenLayers.

The GENPAT platform is derived from the OHEJP COHESIVE project results. In particular, it extends the CIS (COHESIVE Information System) for Italian needs. The system has been also used in the national project of the “Italian One-Health JointDB” where a pilot has been conducted on *Listeria monocytogenes* to integrate data from ISS (storing isolates from human clinical cases) and GENPAT (storing animal, food and environmental isolates) using a mechanism based on federated servers.

Figures 4 and 5. Two examples of WGS data illustrated in the GENPAT dashboard. GENPAT, IZSAM, Italy.

OH-EpiCap tool (ANSES, France & UoS, UK)

OH-EpiCap Tool: Evaluation tool for OH epidemiological surveillance capacities and capabilities. The OH-EpiCap tool aims to develop system-specific profiles of (potential) surveillance interoperability between sectors, highlighting both strengths and gaps in surveillance capacities and capabilities.

5.1. Data

The OH-EpiCap tool allows evaluation and improvement of “One Health-ness” using a set of standardized indicators, which allows comparison across systems, countries and hazards of interest. Countries at similar levels of “One Health-ness”, including similar capacities, limitations and resources, can potentially collaborate to develop a common framework for OHS that will address zoonotic threats across borders. This will improve national OH structures, including surveillance and data analysis, while also facilitating better integration of multinational collaboration. Countries at different levels of “One Health-ness” and surveillance capacities/resources can share experiences regarding surveillance practice against the same pathogen, transfer knowledge and share ideas to improve surveillance quality and efficacy across settings.

5.2. Layout

The OH-EpiCap tool facilitates discussion between surveillance representatives from different disciplines and programs, encouraging a more collaborative OH approach. It is based on a standalone interactive web-based application, which allows a panel with representatives from all sectors within the system being evaluated to complete an in-country surveillance evaluation. The tool focuses on evaluating “One Health-ness” across three dimensions:

- Dimension 1: Organization of the OHS system
- Dimension 2: “One Health-ness” in operational activities of the OHS system
- Dimension 3: Impact of the OHS system

Some of the features of the tool include:

- Evaluation of “One Health-ness” across the three dimensions
- Interactive visualisation of results
- Benchmarking tool to compare to other OHS systems

5.3. Technical implementation

The OH-EpiCap tool has been developed by the MATRIX consortium. One activity of activity of MATRIX has been the development of the generic benchmarking tool presented here, for characterising, monitoring, and evaluating epidemiological surveillance capacities and capabilities, which directly contribute to OHS. The tool aims to identify and describe the collaborations among actors involved in the surveillance of a hazard and to characterize the “One Health-ness” of the surveillance system. The tool will support identification of areas that could lead to improvements in existing OHS capacities.

More information is available here: [OH-EpiCap tool flyer](#) and [OH-EpiCap tool user guide](#). The OH-EpiCap tool itself is available at <https://freddietafreeth.shinyapps.io/OH-EpiCap/>.

RESAPATH Online (ANSES, France)

<https://shiny-public.anses.fr/ENresapath2/>

The RESAPATH is the French network for surveillance of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in bacterial pathogens isolated from diseased animals. It monitors AMR rates and trends in France.

6.1. Data

Data collected include all the results of antibiotic susceptibility tests carried out by RESAPATH member laboratories at the request of practicing veterinarians in the context of their health care activities. RESAPATH data are freely accessible via an interactive open-access web English interface (see link above).

6.2. Layout & technical implementation

This dashboard, updated once a year in the fall, was designed with R Shiny (a library of web development for the statistical software R). A custom stylesheet in CSS was developed to improve visual appeal. Graphs were created using specific R libraries (ggplot2, plotly). This interface allows the visualisation of results by selecting different combinations of interest (year/animal species/bacteria/pathology/antibiotic). Data are presented through three tabs:

- General data: number of antibiograms;
- Antimicrobial susceptibility tables: proportion of susceptible strains;
- Trends: curves of temporal evolution of the proportions of susceptible isolates with their 95% confidence intervals. All graphs are downloadable as images along with their associated data in Excel© format.

RESAPATH on line

anses RESAPATH

About ▾ General data ▾ Susceptibility tables Resistance trends FR

About ▾ General data ▾ Susceptibility tables Resistance trends FR

Choose animal specie

Poultry ▾

Choose a pathology-bacteria-age combination

- All pathologies - E. coli - Laying hens (table & hatching eggs)
- All pathologies - E. coli - Broilers
- All pathologies - E. coli - Turkeys
- All pathologies - E. coli - Ducks
- All pathologies - E. coli - Guinea-fowls
- All pathologies - E. coli - Hens-Broilers
- All pathologies - Staphylococcus aureus - Hens-Broilers
- All pathologies - Enterococcus cecorum - Hens-Broilers

Figures 6, 7, 8. Screenshots illustrating the RESAPATH user interface, available selection criteria and the resulting visualisation from those criteria. RESAPATH Online, ANSES, France.

SARS-BOARD (INIA-CSIC, Spain)

<https://gis.inia.es/portal/apps/opsdashboard/index.html#/5d44a9b0d8fc427e836dd266ef1125a6>

The aim of the SARS-BOARD dashboard is to provide an interactive tool for exploring SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks in all types of animals (captive, domestic, wild and pets).

The dashboard was authored by the [Epidemiology and Environmental Health](#) group at the Center for Animal Health Research (CISA), INIA-CSIC. It was funded by and developed within the OHEJP [COVRIN](#) project. GIS development was done by [Innvel](#).

7.1. Data

- **SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks:** [World Animal Health Information System](#) (WAHIS) of the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH, formerly OIE). Weekly download of notifications.
- **Climate data:** [Climate Data Online](#) (CDO)
- **Socioeconomical factors:** [World Bank Data](#)

7.2. Definitions of Animal Types

- **Captive:** Refers to wild animals with phenotypes unaffected by human selection but that are captive, for example zoo animals
- **Domestic:** Livestock or farms (including fur farms)
- **Wild:** an animal that has a phenotype unaffected by human selection and lives independent of direct human supervision or control. Included here are feral animals (animals of a domesticated species that now live without direct human supervision or control)
- **Pets:** animals that live directly under human supervision or control, typically for companionship (dogs, cats, rabbits, etc.)

7.3. Layout

The SARS-BOARD contains three tabs:

1. The historical outbreak records tab is the main page for exploring and visualising data. This section includes map of SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks in animals from 2020 to present at the top, a time slider of outbreak notifications at the bottom, and a list of interactive graphics on the right related to the region of the total or selection of outbreaks that could be developed in the map or in the time graphic. The time slider tool enables users to wind back time and view the global situation at any given moment since 2020, as well as to select time periods by species and regions. By clicking on any outbreak, a pop-up window with outbreak information appears.
2. The tab "Country data" includes an interactive historical map of monthly mean temperatures and SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks in animals. Each monthly temperature layer can be turned on and off as an interactive background map. Potential socioeconomic factors related to SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks notifications in animals have been included.
3. The tab "World globe" allows users to explore SARS-CoV-2 outbreak notifications in animals on the entire globe including a place search tool.

7.4. Technical implementation

The technical platform of choice was [ArcGIS](#).

Sykdomspulsen One Health (FHI/NIPH & NVI, Norway)

The Sykdomspulsen One Health website is a pilot project for the surveillance of *Campylobacter* infections in Norway. It is a collaboration between the Norwegian Institute of Public Health, the Norwegian Veterinary Institute and the Norwegian Food Safety Authorities. It is currently a closed website.

8.1. Data

The data used on the website were *Campylobacter* tests of broiler flocks, doctor's consultation data and weather data. In addition to showing the plain data in the website, models were made to forecast and display potential gastro-intestinal outbreaks in humans. Every week, all data was being automatically retrieved, cleaned, analysed and displayed as graphs and maps on the website. The testing of broiler flocks started in 2006 and runs every year from May to October. More information is available in a poster presented at the University of Oslo for the 2021 One Health in the 21st Century conference ([see page 3](#)).

8.2. Layout

The website is structured in a traditional way, with a navigation bar at the top of the page, and a set of tabs and subtabs to structure information (Figure 9). There are different sections for gastro-intestinal diseases in Norway, *Campylobacter*-specific surveillance, general information about OH, and a glossary based on the [OHEJP ORION Glossary](#). Data and forecasts are being displayed as interactive graphs and maps where the user can choose the time frame and geographical area of their choice (Figures 10 and 11).

8.3. Technical implementation

The website is developed entirely with Shiny, a library of web development for the statistical software R. Additionally, we wrote a custom stylesheet in CSS to improve visual appeal and user-friendliness. Graphs and maps make use of some specific R libraries (leaflet, splmaps, ggplot2). The automatization of data flow is handled by Sykdomspulsen Analytics, which is an implementation of the generic Sykdomspulsen Core framework (available in the form of an open-source R package). It requires a Linux server, a database, and a set of container images (i.e. lightweight virtual machines). More information can be found [here](#).

Figure 9. Picture of the Sykdomspulsen One Health website with navigation bar at the top consisting of a One-Health page, a Veterinary Institute data page and a Institute of Public health page and tabs underneath. Developed by FHI/NIPH and NVI, Norway.

Figure 10. Three different graphs showing how the data is visualised in the Sykdomspulsen One Health website. Sykdomspulsen One Health, FHI/NIPH and NVI, Norway.

Figure 11. A map of Norway with signals based on the forecast model. Sykdomspulsen One Health, FHI/NIPH and NVI, Norway.

TSIS – TierSeuchenInformationssystem / Animal Diseases Information System (FLI, Germany)

<https://tsis.fli.de/>

The TierSeuchenInformationssystem (TSIS), otherwise known as the Animal Diseases Information System, makes up-to-date information on notifiable animal diseases in Germany available to the public. The system allows for interactive searching of animal disease outbreaks in Germany, provides information on the status of notifiable infectious animal diseases in Germany and respective restriction zones. Notifiable animal diseases are infections of animals that are subject to national control programmes due to their economic importance or their risks for livestock or human health. In Germany, control measures are implemented by the federal states (Länder). The competent veterinary authorities must notify the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture about all animal disease outbreaks that occur in their area of responsibility. Notification occurs via electronic data transmission through use of the software "TSN", i.e. TierSeuchenNachrichten System (animal disease news system), which is only accessible to the approved authorities.

However, these notifications form the basis of the TSIS and make appropriate information on the current AH situation in Germany accessible to the public. TSIS also contains information on previous animal disease outbreaks, individual epidemics and the functioning of national control measures. As a result, TSIS provides all those interested in AH with quick and easy access to up-to-date information on the AH situation in Germany.

9.1. Data and technical implementation

Notifiable animal disease data are collected into TSN, a relational database management system based on the Microsoft SQL server software. Limited data from TSN, including the disease, the species affected, the state and district within which the disease occurred, the date of detection and any restriction zones implemented in response to the notification are made available to the public through the TSIS web interface. The TSIS web interface uses the ASP.NET framework software and (C#) programming language.

9.2. Layout

The TSIS web interface is structured with a navigation bar at the top of the page with menu options 'Startseite'(Home page), 'Tierseuchenlage'(Animal disease situation), 'Service'(Resources) and 'Impressum'(About). The option 'Tierseuchenlage' provides the user with three further options 'Tiersucheninformationen' (Animal disease information), 'Amtlicher Monatsbericht' (Official Monthly report) and 'Tiergesundheitsjahresberichte' (AH annual reports). When the user selects the option 'Tiersucheninformationen' they are taken to a page presenting all the notifiable diseases for which a report is available. If the user then selects a disease of interest from the list, they arrive at a page listing all the reports available for that disease. The user can filter the information by case status (active or inactive), animal type (domestic or wild), disease occurrence date (can be a range), location (state and/or region), pathogen details, and/or association with a restriction zone. The data are visualised in tabular form. Cases can also be visualised geographically through overlay over a map of Germany. At this time, the data cannot be exported, however, planned updates to the system will allow this function in the future.

INSA, Portugal

Considering the OH concept there is no report which includes human, animal and environmental health. However, there are reports for human and AH separately.

Regarding the human health reports, they are annually published by the General Directorate of Health ([DGS](#)) and are related to viral hepatitis, tuberculosis and prevention and control of infections and AMR.

Concerning the AH reports, they are annually published by the General Directorate of Food and Veterinary ([DGAV](#)) and are related to some zoonoses that affect the animals in Portugal, such as bovine tuberculosis, bovine brucellosis, *Salmonella*, among others.

At this moment, a dashboard that includes animal and human health is not planned.

Recommendations for sustainability

Sustainability is an important aspect for all deliverables of data and information to users, either dashboards or other material, and needs to be considered to ensure that the information remains available and relevant.

When investing many hours and effort in making a dashboard, the ultimate goal is usually to achieve a sustainable product. Nonetheless, it is important to investigate the capabilities for sustainability even early in the dashboard work. All the different components need to be taken into consideration and checked for sustainability. This includes the different datasets used, the platform for analysis of data, the components feeding the dashboard with data and the dashboard itself. The personnel and finances required for maintaining and improving a dashboard is also an important aspect that needs to be kept in mind to achieve a sustainable product.

The MATRIX sustainability strategy was included in the project proposal and work plan. One of the sentences in the document was “The sustainability of the outputs from MATRIX lies primarily with each country that chooses to adopt the proposed frameworks”. In this way, the different institutions that have produced the dashboards listed above are the ones responsible for the sustainability of their products. As for the dashboard inventory itself (and the accompanying DIC), its sustainability will be ensured by the leaders of WP6. The development method and infrastructure behind the DIC has been selected with sustainability in mind – more about this can be read in deliverable D-WP6.1.

The Disease Dashboards project developed by SVA, Sweden has taken sustainability into consideration from the start. Data access is secured by the IT department whose responsibility it is to manage the LIMS and the databases. The data analysis pipelines are robust and maintained regularly by epidemiologists and other topic experts to ensure that the outputs remain correct and relevant. The dashboards themselves will be hosted on an SVA-hosted platform, maintained by the IT department. The outputs displayed in the dashboard will be continually reviewed by disease experts, developers and the communications department to ensure that they remain relevant and fulfil all requirements regarding accessibility and useability.

The Sykdomspulsen One Health dashboard developed by FHI/NIPH and NVI, Norway, has been a very stable and sustainable system throughout the MATRIX project. The data access, analysis pipelines and website are based on automated systems and the collaboration with NVI was planned to continue for at least one more year after the MATRIX project ends. However, because of budget cuts FHI/NIPH are now reducing their projects and staff, and it is not yet known if the Sykdomspulsen One Health project will be affected. This shows that despite a good sustainability plan and robust systems, external factors can cause changes in the sustainability. The information about the Sykdomspulsen One Health project and description of analysis and technical implementations will anyway be found in the DIC and in a peer-reviewed open-access paper (Swanson et al, 2022 ²). In this way, other people can read about the project and use this information.

² Swanson, D., Koren, C., Hopp, P., Jonsson, M.E., Rø, G.I., White, R.A., Grøneng, G.M., 2022. A One Health real-time surveillance system for nowcasting *Campylobacter* gastrointestinal illness outbreaks, Norway, week 30 2010 to week 11 2022. *Eurosurveillance*.

Conclusion and further directions

This project has contributed to improved collaboration and knowledge-sharing about OHS and the different types of dashboards and interactive tools produced in all the institutions and countries that have participated. This deliverable includes information from eight institutions with different types of dashboards. This information is of very good help for people who are in the start-up phase of developing a dashboard and who want to get more knowledge and inspiration from different possible implementations. In the DIC there is also contact information to the institutions who have been collaborating in the project so that it is easy to contact the people behind the dashboards if there are any additional questions and comments. The rest of the DIC (further described in deliverable D-WP6.1) forms, together with the information about different dashboards, a robust base for people who want to start producing an OHS dashboard.

In addition to providing guidance for other people wanting to make a dashboard, this project has allowed people in different institutions and countries to get to form new connections and collaborate. This causes extensive knowledge transfer across institutions and countries and great discussions around the topic of OHS dashboards. This is important for further work and improvement of the OH – in this case especially focused on dashboards.

The DIC and the dashboards will be maintained far beyond the end of this project and will hopefully be of great help for developers for many years to come.